

Antibody Characterization Report for Spatacsin

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Spatacsin

Alternative protein name: Colorectal carcinoma-associated protein, Spastic paraplegia 11 protein

Gene name: *SPG11*

Uniprot: Q96JI7

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. This report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for Spatacsin. We used an antibody characterization pipeline [2] based on knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of commercial antibodies for Spatacsin by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. An HAP1 *SPG11* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of Spatacsin in HAP1 is adequate as determined by searching DepMap [3].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the Spatacsin antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Proteintech	16555-1-AG	42377	AB_2925170	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.267	other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	702776**	2109608	AB_2725406	recombinant-mono	2H25L11	rabbit	0.5	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	711811**	2021297	AB_2716913	recombinant-poly	2HCLC	rabbit	0.5	Wb,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, **=recombinant antibody

Table 2: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC007971c006	CVCL_C6IE	HAP1	SPG11 KO
Abcam	ab255448	CVCL_0030	HeLa	WT

Figure 1: Spatacsin antibody screening by immunoblot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *SPG11* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for immunoblot with the indicated Spatacsin antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: 16555-1-AG at 1/200, 702776** at 1/200, and 711811** at 1/200. Predicted band size: 279 kDa. **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Spatacsin antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated Spatacsin antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A. Samples were washed and processed for immunoblot with the indicated Spatacsin antibody. For immunoblot, 702776** was used at 1/200. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Arrows point to Spatacsin or to a non-specific band (n/s). SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: Spatacsin antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *SPG11* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with glass bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated Spatacsin antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody dilution used: 16555-1-AG at 1/300, 702776** at 1/500 and 711811** at 1/500. Bars = 10 µm. **=recombinant antibody

Figure 1: Spatacsin antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: Spatacsin antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: Spatacsin antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested Spatacsin antibodies are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 62-6520 and 65-6120). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21424 and A21429).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by immunoblot

Immunoblots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [4]. HAP1 WT and *SPG11* KO were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and immunoblot. HiMark™ Pre-stained Protein Standard from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number LC5699) was used.

Immunoblots were performed with precast midi 3-8% Tris-Acetate polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1601BOX) ran with Tris-Acetate SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number LA0041), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual immunoblot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% bovine serum albumin in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with HyBlot CL autoradiography films from Denville (cat. number 1159T41).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D). Tubes were rocked for ~2 hrs at 4°C followed by several washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates are rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~2 hrs at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and immunoblot on precast midi 3-8% Tris-Acetate polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1601BOX).

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. HAP1 WT and *SPG11* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in 96 well glass plates (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary Spatacsin antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro widefield high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.45 air immersion objective and scientific CMOS camera, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (Lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa568 and Cellmask Red,

respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns. Three images per field were acquired at a z-interval of 4 microns. Then, best focus intensity projections were generated from the z-stack. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

References

1. Laflamme, C., et al., *Opinion: Independent third-party entities as a model for validation of commercial antibodies*. N Biotechnol, 2021. **65**: p. 1-8 DOI: 10.1016/j.nbt.2021.07.001.
2. Laflamme, C., et al., *Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72*. Elife, 2019. **8** DOI: 10.7554/eLife.48363.
3. Ghandi, M., et al., *Next-generation characterization of the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia*. Nature, 2019. **569**(7757): p. 503-508 DOI: 10.1038/s41586-019-1186-3.
4. Ayoubi, R., P.S. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody Screening by Immunoblot*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717510>.
5. Ayoubi, R., et al., *Antibody screening by Immunoprecipitation*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717516>.
6. Alshafie, W., P. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody screening by Immunofluorescence*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717498>.